

A STUDY OF AI & 3S2T MARKETING AND ITS IMPACT ON CONSUMER BUYING DECISION MAKING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO FASHION INDUSTRY AT MORADABAD

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research paper is to examine the impact of Artificial Intelligence and 3S2T Marketing i.e. Sight, Sound, Smell, Touch and Taste on consumer buying decision with special reference to fashion industry. Last three years has been a boon for marketing and artificial intelligence as all the major companies are using artificial intelligence to allure their customer and enhancing their sales. There is a cut throat competition in the market and companies leave no stone unturned to capture market share. Fashion industry has already been a silver spoon child in the market where elite category customer attracted more towards it. Companies are pondering how to motivate these HNI customers so that they can buy more products and company get more profit. The paper is exploratory in nature SPSS software has been used for statistical analysis.

KEYWORDS: HNI (High Net worth Index), 3S2T Marketing - Sight, Smell, Sound, Touch, Taste (Sensory marketing), Artificial Intelligence, Fashion industry, HNI customer

1. INTRODUCTION

During last few decades the marketing has changed radically, from transactional marketing and uni-dimensional communication to multi-dimensional communication channels. The attention to aim specified target has shifted towards targeting five senses has grown exponentially [1]. Sensory marketing can be described as a marketing strategy that connects customers' senses and influence their perception, reactions, judgments & actions. For business viewpoint it can be used to create intuitive triggers to affect consumer insight [1]. It is a marketing phenomenon that aims to engage the buyer by using his sensations to manipulate his feeling and behavior. It can be executed in five different ways i.e. Sight, Smell, Sound, Taste & Touch [2]. Researches outline the conviction that we feel and connect with the world by using our sensory organs and as a customer our feelings have a considerable influence on the decisions we draw ahead of our perception. Primarily, sensory marketing advocates the scenario where a customer gets sensory know-how that adds worth to their utilization and consumptions of products and services. Technological advancements in retail industry has proposed a more arousing and unforeseen customer experience, fascinating the needs of customers through the five human senses i.e. Sight, Smell, Sound, Touch and Taste [3].

Artificial intelligence has arrived recently and is quickly altering the way we recognize and comprehend marketing. Surprisingly, AI is an advantageous resource and is going to continue to contribute till we utilize it properly. The foremost benefit is how well the Artificial Technology has influenced marketers' ability to observe and figure out consumer shopping behavior. Nowadays, organizations from major industries are using AI technology to save operating costs, boosts productivity, sales, and predict client behavior to improve the overall buyer's shopping experience. Business organizations have to now employ the best AI skilled human resources in order to lead the competition as AI technological advancements. AI possibly will be the answer given the massive

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quantity of data that already exists and the occurrence of data violation. Additionally, organizations can no longer depend on conservative business strategies to endorse expansion due to the complexity of customers' needs and their continuously changing preferences. Artificial Intelligence and marketing strategies have been working together closely during past few years. Major business operations like human resource management, finance, operations & Productions and marketing are quickly putting together AI and ML based technologies. Artificial intelligence has certainly changed marketing.

AI is constantly increasing its presence in a number of ways: from Siri to chatbots (such as the Amazon Echo), to Google's Alexa (which is now available as a chatbot on iOS), and even predictive analytics in some cases. This has led to a lot of people being surprised. With the current state of AI, businesses can now target customers in a more effective and efficient way. AI is changing the way we market. With the current state of AI, businesses can now target customers in a more effective and efficient way. AI has revolutionized marketing and helped to change the way people interact with the world. This has led to new strategies and innovative ways to revolutionize their products, services, and campaigns. The study is looking at how customers feel about how their products are received. Companies analyze previous marketing campaigns to see how customers are reacting. They are looking for patterns and patterns of behavior that suggest potential customers. They are also looking for companies that have a good reputation and are not afraid to tell it like it is. With the help of AI, they learn what content is getting the most positive engagements, so they show more posts of what customers want to see.

Sensory marketing encompasses many techniques used to reach into the minds of your customers and influence their buying behavior depending upon how your brand and plans make them feel. Using media minds in promotional and marketing movements can have a major impact on your potential customers and their decisions to pay for your brand.

Source: [4]

Fig. 1: <<Caption Needed>>

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Customers' and marketers' interest in online consumption has grown remarkably due to the changes in technological, social, political and environmental concerns. Though the growth is not completely quantitative because customer not only wants a product but also want an experience and pleasing environment. This includes the sensory sensitivity for goods and services [5].

The steady progression of approach towards online sensory media has not been adequately captured in most of the secondary sources of literature. The growing cut throat competition and homogeneous products make it trickier for the marketers to attract customers online by using sensory marketing. Because traditionally sensory aspects work on physical purchase of products [6].

With the increased use of internet and WWW applications, users are gradually more interacting & interfacing with internet based applications. The report put emphasis on four categories of concerning with the quality of web content including: Preciseness, Quality, Appearance & technical competency of content [7].

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People are constantly purchasing and consuming products online where the sensory communications are primarily limited to audio and visuals only. However, marketers are trying to make available other sensory interfaces such as touch, taste and smell by using creative and engaging content [6].

These sensations from various sensory organs may effect in consumers' desire for features of a brand in place of only audio-visual communication attributes shared by traditional marketers. These sensory attributes helps to develop sensations and perceptions to develop buyer decision making process. There are numerous researches have been conducted to understand and test the influence of sensory marketing on buyer's buying behavior signifying the positive effects for marketers [8].

There has been much development of digital sensory enabling techniques in human & computer interactions over the last few years. These technologies include Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR), but their uses are still at the early stage in marketing domain as far as the customer acquisition is concerned. These technological advancements can be revolutionized in the field of digital marketing aiming towards engaging human senses [9].

Due to the growth of handy and personified equipments, highly engaging and communicative physical & virtual links, the customer experience is developing into new types of understanding where a customer can get multi sensory experiences through digital devices; however it is still in its early stage and needs to get evolved to acquire more customers in present internet era [10].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀) - There is no impact of Age on shopping experience through AI.

Alternate Hypothesis (H₁) - There is a significant impact of age on shopping behavior through AI.

The objectives of current research are -

- To study the impact of age on shopping experience through AI.
- To examine the importance of AI in customer buying decision making process.
- To study the 3S2T i.e. sight, sound, smell, touch & taste and its impact on consumer buying decisions.

3.2 Research Design:

This is an exploratory research. 100 costumers are taken for the survey. All belong to the Moradabad district.

3.3 Statistical tool:

All data is analyzed by the MS-Office application software by conducting T test and calculation of Mean data.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

As per the research questions and their responses the data was analyzed through MS-Excel application and T-test and mean was calculated to find out the outcome of study. The variables which have been taken as a part of the study are age and shopping experience through artificial intelligence. As per the data collected from the respondents through close ended questionnaire out of which 48% were female and 52% were male respondents, the average age of respondents was analyzed 27.42 years. Assumed mean difference was decided at 30 years to find out whether age is really a factor which is affected by Artificial Intelligence to influence sensory organs or not. For the first objective it was observed that there is a significant impact of age on impact of AI on shopping experience through sensory marketing.

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	27.42	0
Variance	30.67030303	0
Observations	100	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	30	
df	99	
t Stat	-4.658656318	
P(T<=t) one-tail	4.96213E-06	
t Critical one-tail	1.660391157	
P(T<=t) two-tail	9.92425E-06	
t Critical two-tail	1.9842169	

Figure 1. T-test

It was identified that the majority of respondents buy jewelry/ornaments from online medium by using Artificial Intelligence followed by eye wear and fashion accessory with a mean of 0.85, 0.75 and 0.65 respectively. Majority of the respondents accepted that Artificial intelligence influence their Sight as a sensory organ with a mean of 0.86 for highly influence and 0.12 for influence. As far as the impact of AI on smell sense was concerned majority of the population was not much confident that AI influences the smell as a promotional tool; 0.26 was the mean of respondents having less influence and respondents with 0.24 were neutral on this question. Respondents with a total average of 0.96 were agreed that AI influence the sound as a sense to attract customers. Majority of the respondents were neutral with an average of 0.4 on the impact on AI on Taste but an average of 0.46 were influenced and 0.18 were somewhere influenced on the impact of AI tools on touch as a sensory statement.

A significant number of respondents were in favor of the statement that Artificial intelligence provide personalized experience for your sensory organs, it provides best quality of services for the concerned sensory organ and it provide hassle free service and enhance customer experience by influencing your sensory organs.

5. CONCLUSION

With the overall respondents' data and its analysis it can be interpreted that Artificial Intelligence provides hassle free shopping environment, gives a real sensation to customer's sensory organs and thus enhance the overall shopping experience of customers. Artificial intelligence is going to be one of the most interactive tools for the marketers who want to expand their market share and looking to acquire more customers in order to survive in the competitive market. Artificial intelligence is the interactive tool through which marketers can easily communicate with their target customers and influence their sensations. Sensory marketing, as it is one of the newest terminologies in the world of marketing management can easily be implemented by using artificial intelligence techniques. Various senses of a customer such as eyes, ears, nose, skin and tongue can be sensitized by the usage of artificial intelligence techniques by targeting sight, sound, smell, touch and taste sensations.

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